

THE COMPLETION OF CREATION

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10422730>

Published Date: 22-December-2023

Abstract: With the calculus wrong, ¹which we overturned, the wrong equations of the kinematic material body were derived. For the same reason it turned out to be a centripetal force, different from the real one we give, and does not support the heliocentric system and Bohr's atom. Mistakes were made by Joule in the thermomechanical and thermoelectric equivalents and in the calculation of the power unit. The principle of conservation of energy does not apply, which is also overturned experimentally. The geocentric system of the world is being restored. A new atomic theory is created, which stems from the author's worldview. A new form of electricity is created, challenging the strict acceptance of Ohm's law.

It turns out the correct centripetal force.

It provides the structure of the universes predicted by my worldview and describes God's creation as incomplete. Operators-equations for the creation of superverses are proposed, which will act as molds of creation, as was done in the creation of matter by God.

INTRODUCTION

The completion of creation is the completion of what the Gods (God and Goddess) created, namely the universes (one-dimensional-line-, two-dimensional-plane-, three-dimensional-regular tetrahedron-) and all this within the universal bubble. And also, our six compressed sphere universes corresponding to the faces of the cube and inscribed the central bubble, of three dimensions with an additional dimension of time belonging to the goddess. They also created the universes corresponding to the seats of the regular hexahedron and have the six universes three dimensions and with one of time belonging to the goddess, as in the cube and our own universes, the same. These universes share intersecting spaces with ours.

As well as the twelve super-universes corresponding to the seats of a regular dodecahedron with three dimensions plus two of time, one dimension belongs to the god and the other to the goddess. They have inscribed the central bubble and its universes have intersections with our own, common spaces.

For these universes and super-universes, we will formulate the conditions and laws that exist and their mathematical formation that will be given are the molds on which the whole was built. There remain the twenty super-universes of three dimensions plus three of time, one belonging to the god, the other to the goddess and the third to the writer, who becomes a potential creator. The plan of all universes and super-universes will be sent by ethereal waves instantaneously to the core of the control center of the universes, where the conditions and laws of matter are realized, and supplemented by the conditions and laws of the author.

First, we must repeat what we have modified and modify those treaties that have not been modified, in order to enter into the structure of the Whole. We will use the difference mathematics we have proposed²

¹ «ALEKOS CHARALAMPOPOULOS, OVERTURNING OF INFINITESIMAL CALCULUS AND RESTORATION OF THE MATHEMATICS IN CONNECTION WITH THE COSMIC THEORY "THE IDION" International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, Oct2020-Mar2021»

² «ALEKOS CHARALAMPOPOULOS, OVERTURNING OF INFINITESIMAL CALCULUS AND RESTORATION OF THE MATHEMATICS IN CONNECTION WITH THE COSMIC THEORY "THE IDION" International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, Oct2020-Mar2021» και στο ίδιο «THE FINAL FORM OF THE ATOMIC THEORY, Oct2023-Mar2024».

METHODOLOGY

Inductive reasoning as well as abductive reasoning is used in this work.

Thus, it forms simple equations implied by definitions, such as velocity and acceleration, or centripetal acceleration predicted by the fundamental equation of velocity of circular rotation of a particle when constant and by inductive reasoning, it reaches the equation of space traveling mobile with acceleration a and the real equation of centripetal acceleration.

Work presupposes principles, axioms, that is, or demands, which it sets for the creation of the worldview and mathematics it uses. Just as the ancient Greek philosophers set the principles for the creation of their theory, or as Einstein set the two axioms for the creation of relativity, so here.

Axioms, or principles or demands, are that zero is something and pre-exists, and matter consists of indivisible parts, whether they are called atoms or other particles.

MODIFICATION OF CONDITIONS AND MATHEMATICS

In a privileged frame system, a particle or body, when moving straight through the system at velocity v , then the body has positions,

$$x=x_0+v_x t, y=y_0+v_y t, z=z_0+v_z t$$

in the Cartesian coordinate system. When the motion is consistently accelerated with acceleration a and zero initial velocity and is linear, then the speed is,

$$v_x=a_x t, v_y=a_y t, v_z=a_z t$$

And then the posts will be,

$$x=x_0+a_x t^2, y=y_0+a_y t^2, z=z_0+a_z t^2$$

See any physics, they give the equations,

$$x=x_0+ \frac{1}{2} a_x t^2, y=y_0+ \frac{1}{2} a_y t^2, z=z_0+ \frac{1}{2} a_z t^2$$

which is wrong, since we with simple mathematics proved that $1/2$ is not needed. This means that the acceleration of gravity, at the earth's surface, is about half of what has been accepted since the wrong formula was used! Also, the pressure of the atmosphere at the earth's surface is half, 5.007×10^4 Nt/met², since the weight measured in Nt is now half!

If the motion is accelerated and in a non-straight line, then in the above equations we need the interval of time that has a constant velocity, Δt , with which we will substitute t in the equations.

ENERGY AND POWER

The power is $F=ma=m\Delta x/\Delta t^2$. $x=x_0+vt$, so $\Delta x=v\Delta t$, and since the energy is, $E=ma\Delta x$ (the force is exerted over a distance interval Δx). Then it is deduced from these equations and the energy is,

$$E_{kin}=m\Delta v^2=m(v_f-v_i)^2=mv_f^2+mv_i^2-2mv_i v_f$$

If the initial velocity is zero, then the kinetic energy is $E_{kin}=mv_f^2$ and twice as much as Joule $A=2$ Joules, the unit of energy, and Watt $A=2$ Watts, the unit of power.

In all cases, force was applied to finally gain a velocity of the body, or particle, and in the initial conditions of creation of the universe, which were all stationary, initial forces were exerted. So, if a body has an initial velocity of zero and is at some height h from the center of the earth, but Δh from the surface of the earth, then the force to fall to the surface is $F=mg$ and the energy the kinetic that will be gained, is, since $\Delta x/\Delta h=k$,

$$E_{kin}=mg\Delta h=km(\Delta x^2/\Delta t^2)=kmv_f^2+kmv_i^2-2kmv_i v_f$$

And because the initial velocity is zero, then $E_{kin}=kmv_f^2$.

In the case of the calculation by Joule,

Device used by Joule to locate the equivalent of mechanical and thermal energy

of the equivalent of mechanical and thermal energy, the formula $J = mg\Delta h / c\Delta T$ was used. Inside the device was mercury, heated by the rotation of fins. Because the rotation of the blades was slow, their kinetic energy was considered zero, only the energy $E = mg\Delta h$ was obtained, and found as calculated $J = 1/4.182 = 0.24$. It was assumed that the energy $E = mg\Delta h$ is equal to the thermal energy acquired by the water and not that this is an experimental result.³

But about the electric-thermal experiment, we should say the following:

Device for electrical-thermal equivalent

I did Joule's electric-thermal experiment as follows:

I took a piece of plastic pipe, plumbing 22 cm and 3.2 cm in diameter, closed it with metal lids and connected the caps to an electrical voltage source, having first filled it with water.

Before the experiment, I operated the power source and it consumed 27 watts. When I connected it, the system consumed 81 Watts. The voltage was 800 Volts and the electric current 54.6 mAmp. The electrical power $P_{Ohm} = V_{Ohm}I = R_{Ohm}I^2$ was 43.7 Watts. The water was $m = 53$ gr, so in $\Delta t = 110$ sec the water temperature rose 5 grad C^0 . Water acquired thermal energy, after using $c = 4.182$ Joule/gr.grad, and the power was,

$$P_{Th} = mc\Delta T / \Delta t = 10.3 \text{ Watts.}$$

So $81 \text{ Watt} = 27 + 43.7 + 10.3$ was consumed in the system and the electrical power $P_{Ohm} = V_{Ohm}I = R_{Ohm}I^2$ passed through the pipeline-water (43.7 Watt) and 27 Watts were consumed from the source and 10.3 Watt increased the heat power of the water and took it from the electrical power of the water pipeline when current passes. The electric thermal equivalent $J = 0.24$ was verified by introduction to formula $c = 4.182$ Joules, so, the thermal energy was less than its electrical conductor ($10.3/43.7 = 0.24$). But with the input $c = 4.182$ Joules, so I found 0.24 twice, since $1 \text{ Joule} / c = 0.24$, which is an experimental overturning of the electric-thermal equivalent!

³ ELEMENTS OF PHYSICS, Kougioumtzilis-Peristerakis, p. 582

Because the unit of power Watt_A is twice the acceptable one, and because $m_1c=mg\Delta h/\Delta T$ and g are half of what is acceptable, then $c=0.5 \times 4.182$ Joules and because Joule_A=2 Joules we found $c_A=0.5 \times 2 \times 4.182$ Joules=4.182 Joules_A, i.e. the electric thermal equivalent remains the same as calculated, let's have made the modifications.

For the calculation of the unit of electricity, the formula should be used experimentally,

$$P=V_{OhmI}=R_{OhmI}^2= \frac{1}{2} mv^2/t$$

considering equal electrical energy converted into mechanical.

But we calculated the kinetic energy $E_{kin} = mv^2$, when the force is applied by Δt , from an initial velocity of zero.

HOW THEY EXPERIMENTALLY DETERMINED THE POWER UNIT

The power of a small electric motor⁴ was measured as follows:

Εικ. 151. Μέτρηση της αποδιδόμενης ισχύος

They rotated a small electric motor, as in the figure, and he rotated a pulley. The pulley carried a special rope, which was tied and stretched with two dynamometers. The deviation of the dynamometers was the force F , multiplied by the frequency of engine f and the length of pulley circumference L Power was $P=F.f.L$.

Apparently, they measured potential and kinetic energy, which was twice as high, as we noted. From this experiment and because the engine was powered by electrical power $P=VI$, they equated it with the measurement of dynamometers and the frequency and length of circumference of the pulley. And apparently, they assumed that the principle of conservation of energy, converted from electrical to mechanical, applies.

OVERTURNING THE PRINCIPLE OF ENERGY CONSERVATION

From the experiment I did on the electric-thermal equivalent, I suspected that the principle of conservation of energy does not apply. And I did another experiment.

I took a small motor and propeller with small fins and made a fan. It worked with 6 Volt DC. I measured in operation of the fan in the air with the supplied voltage device, consumed 11.1 watts. I put the rotating blades inside a water basin, so they rotated slowly, for 300 sec. Now fan and device, they consumed 12.4 watts. So, the electrical power consumed to rotate the blades in the water was 1.3 watts. At 300 seconds the water temperature which was 4 liters, 4000 gr, rose by 0.2 degrees Celsius. That is, the power from the rise in temperature rose by,

$$P_{Th}=mc\Delta T/t=4000 \times 4.182 \times 0.2/300= 11.15 \text{ Watt.}$$

We see that the electric power of 1.2 Watt, gave with the mechanical movement of the blades, a power of rise in water, 11.15 Watt.

Experimentally with both experiments I did, the principle of conservation of energy does not apply, in conversions from electrical to mechanical and thermal and obviously vice versa. But the equivalent conversion of mechanical and potential energy, pulsating mass tied to a spring, or gravity applies.

⁴ PHYSICS, THE HISTORY OF ENERGY, H. Emmet Brown-Edward Schwachtgen, p.205

ELECTRICAL VOLTAGE AND ELECTRICITY

The electric current is $I=q/t=Ne/t=NeL/Lt$, L = length of the conductor where the electrical voltage is applied. And the load velocity $v=L/t$ and $v=IL/Ne$.

But in the conductor by exerting the electric voltage, an electric field of $E=f=V/L$ and $F=eEf=eV/L=ma=m\Delta x/\Delta t^2$ was generated. So,

$$V=(m/e)L\Delta x/\Delta t^2=k(m/e)v^2$$

Because the initial velocity of electric charges was zero before the electrical voltage was applied, $V=k(m/e)v^2$

k is a coefficient of proportion and proportional of the electrical resistance R interfering with the electrical circuit. It is, $I=q/t=NeL/Lt=Ne v/L$.

Substitute $v=IL/Ne$ and,

$$V=k(mL^2/N^2e^3)I^2.$$

If $N/L=n$ is the linear charge density, then,

$$V=k(m/n^2e^3)I^2$$

But $k(m/n^2e^3)=R$, the resistance. Then

$$V_{1/2}=V_{Ohm}=R_{1/2}I=R_{Ohm}I$$

When $R_{Ohm}=1$ Ohm, $R=1$ Ohm_A and $I=1$ Amp, then $V=1$ Volt_A

The 1 Amp unit was determined in the electrolysis of $AgNO_3$ and is arbitrary. They also took electrical resistance, R Ohm = 1 Ohm⁵ as the resistor that has a mercury column 106.3 cm long, weighing 14.5 gr and cross section $A = 1$ mm² at 0 °C, to satisfy the formula 1 Watt = 1 Ohm. 1 Amp² = 1 Volt. Amp and 1 Watt they found it with the formula we already gave.

Therefore also 1 Volt_{Ohm} = $R_{Ohm}I$ and,}

$$1 \text{ Watt} = 1 \text{ Volt}_{Ohm}. 1 \text{ Amp} = 0.5 \text{ Watt}_A = 0.5 \text{ Volt}_A. \text{ Amp}_A$$

THE CALIBRATION OF VOLTMETERS AND AMMETERS

When the first ammeters and voltmeters were created, it was close to 1830 AD and then there was no alternating current yet. There were Volta elements from the 1800s, as sources of direct electric current and electrical resistors. To calibrate ammeters and construct them, they must have accepted Ohm's law (1827), which is not an experimental result, but a prerequisite. With a Volta cell, and with a resistor, they received an electric current of one Amp. One Amp was determined by electrolysis, by Faraday (1827). They put a second resistor in the circuit, equal to the first, and calibrated the current as equal to 0.5 Amp. Then they put a third electrical resistance and so on. Then with the first resistor, they put a second Volta source in the circuit, equal to the first, and calibrated the electric current as two amps. And so on with a third resistor and more. So they calibrated the Ammeters they built.

However, they may have calibrated the ammeters in electrolysis by varying the electrical voltage and measuring the amount of Ag (silver) deposited on the cathode. This experimentally.

Then, given the calibration of the electric current and the standard mercury electrical resistance mentioned above, they calibrated one Volt. Given the calibration of the electric current, they varied the electrical voltage and calibrated it the height of the Volts inversely according to the electric current, according to Ohm's law.

In the experiments must have confirmed the formula,

$$1 \text{ Watt} = 1 \text{ Volt}_{Ohm}. 1 \text{ Amp} = 1 \text{ Ohm}. 1 \text{ Amp}^2$$

adjusting the mercury electrical resistance to 106.3 cm, cross section 1mm², to 0 °C, so that they get, as the experiment of measuring motor electrical power quoted, 1 Watt = $1/2$ mv² = $1/2$ kgr.met²/sec².

⁵ ELEMENTS OF PHYSICS, P. Akatos-B. Nerantzis, p. 19

$$BC^2 = 2r^2 = BO^2 + DC^2 = (a_v T^2 / 16)^2 + (a_o T^2 / 16)^2 \text{ and, } a_o^2 + a_v^2 = 512r^2 / T^4.$$

$$a_c = a_v = 16 r / T^2 = 0.4 \omega^2 r = a_o$$

and, $a_c = a_v =$ centripetal acceleration.

The centripetal acceleration that gives the force $F = ma_c$ that the orbiting body has, is equalized by the force of attraction which is gravitational or electric and the body then falls towards the center of the circle, at speed v_v . The permissible acceleration imparts a force $F = ma_o$ to the body and this is equal to the friction force of the ether it crosses, $F = -bv_o$ and $v_o = ma_o / b$.

The traction force is $F = 0.4m\omega^2 r = 0.4m\omega^2 r^4 / r^3 = k / r^3$.

FOR THE PLANETARY SYSTEM

The centripetal acceleration we found overturns the explanation of the moon's orbit, with the law of attraction of masses, when it is inversely proportional to the square of the radius of the two masses. It is $F = m \cdot 0.4v^2 / r = m \cdot 0.4v^2 r^2 / r^3 = kMm / r^3$. The explanation for the moon was given by Newton and is not valid because the inverse square law does not apply.

Also used was the formula, $F = GMm / r^2 = mv^2 / r$, $v = 2\pi r / T$, $T =$ the period of the orbiting celestial body around the sun of mass M . This formula is correct, for motionless masses, as the Cavendish's experiment proves. Also, a same formula is proved of Coulomb, for motionless attracted charges. And,

$$GM / 4\pi^2 = r^3 / T^2$$

Which is a condition introduced by Kepler for the orbits of planets. But now, because we have proved that $a = 0.4v^2 / r$, it becomes, $GM / 4\pi^2 = 0.4r^3 / T^2$, which does not prove the Kepler-Newton condition. Something went wrong.

We proved the inverse cube law, $F = k / r^3$, $r = (F/k)^{1/3}$. If angular momentum is both elliptical and constant, then $vr = L$, $L =$ constant. And $r = L / v$, so,

$$Lk^{1/3} = C = vF^{1/3} = \frac{m^{1/3} v 0.4v^{2/3}}{(r)^{1/3}} = \frac{m^{1/3} 0.4v^{5/3}}{(r)^{1/3}} = \frac{mv^2 0.4(r)^{2/3}}{r m^{2/3} v^{1/3}} = F \frac{(r)^{2/3}}{m^{2/3} v^{1/3}}$$

The angular momentum is not constant in elliptical $F \frac{(r)^{2/3}}{m^{2/3} v^{1/3}}$ motion, because is not constant. In circular motion, it is constant, because then v , r , are constant. This means that the celestial body does not travel equal areas at equal times, the second condition introduced by Kepler.

Spacecraft missions to the moon, Mars and all planetary bodies are designed in a geocentric coordinate system.

THE ONE-DIMENSIONAL CORRESPONDING TO THE 3 DIMENSIONS OF SPACE

From the above, it is extracted,

$$x = x_0 + v_x t \quad \text{and } t = (x - x_0) / v_x$$

$$y = y_0 + v_y t \quad t = (y - y_0) / v_y$$

$$z = z_0 + v_z t \quad t = (z - z_0) / v_z$$

in the Cartesian coordinate system. When the motion is steadily accelerated with acceleration a and is linear, then the positions will be,

$$x = x_0 + a_x t^2 \quad \text{and } t = \{(x - x_0) / a_x\}^{1/2}$$

$$y = y_0 + a_y t^2, \quad t = \{(y - y_0) / a_y\}^{1/2}$$

$$z = z_0 + a_z t^2, \quad t = \{(z - z_0) / a_z\}^{1/2}$$

In these six equations, we find the one-dimension of time, which corresponds to the three dimensions of space. So, it's one dimension, but if we look at it in the coordinate system, it has three dimensions. So the universe we live in is four and six dimensions at the same time, if one sees time as a dimension. And straight away we proceed to the definition of time and space.

DEFINITION OF TIME AND SPACE

As Aristotle states in his Lecture on Nature and St. Augustine in the Confessions, time is movement. Motion of the universe around the axis of the universe in 24 hours, makes us the day, a unit of time and 365.22 days a year, which corresponds to the periodic fluctuation of the earth-sun radius. About 32,000 periodic movements of quartz, makes us the second, unit of time. Since the unit of time is one or many periodic movements of body, body or particle, then time is also movement.

In the reversal of calculus, we argued that there is no limit to zero in matter dx , but there is discrete Δx . This came from the choice of the philosophical principle of indivisibility (atom), what happens in the universe, that is, that there are very few particles, be they atoms or others. This was formulated by Democritus.

It is a fact that either matter has indivisibility (atom), or it is divided into infinity. Science tends to accept that the universe is finite, therefore it has indivisible particles (atoms). We, like Democritus, set as a principle the indivisibility of matter (the atom), which implies in mathematics that there is no limit to zero, derivatives and integrals. And calculus is wrong.

Therefore, the velocity is $\Delta x/\Delta t$, however small Δt may be. In this small time, it occurs when there is body movement, jumping, space shifting, body or body. We consider this time to be in the order of $\Delta t=10^{-32}$ sec. Therefore, the movement of each body is broken down into leaps, space permutations that take place at such times. And time is discontinuous. And speed and acceleration, which are movements, they take place in discontinuous time. This leap, if we look at it absolutely, is a short time, if we look at it in a coordinate system, it is a position vector. And the vector through time is velocity.

A much shorter fraction of time to this, the bubble-particle of dilute ether remains stationary (such a positive-charge particle-bubble and a negative form when a hydrogen atom is bound and when traveling, a photon corresponding to velocity c). Within this shorter time, the gods go through all the equations – operators for the formation of the universes, of matter. And then follows the leap of a longer time interval Δt . Equations can be laws of nature and can be philosophical principles.

Before creation, motion was the movement of zero, the transformation of the ultimate impersonal zero into a male person, and at the same time the self-birth of the goddess. The goddess in her imagination captured infinite points arranged in infinite space and put them in an oscillation of ether volume, which from zero to 90^0 becomes V to 00 degrees or 1800 . The operator was the equation $V=V_0\cos(\omega t+\varphi)$ and with different φ suitable for the points, It became a continuous ether substance alternating into negative and positive and pulsating. The tensile zero was pulsating, because the ether is the tensile zero of matter, the matter we know, and the points from which it comes are dimensionless. This operator (the oscillation equation) caused imagination to become reality and ether, a type of matter, to be an extension of zero in dimensions, that is, to become extensible.

The concept of space comes from the distribution of matter. The distribution of bodies determines finite space, and the distribution of ether points determines infinite space. Before creation, there was no space. Something was dimensionless. There was zero dimensionless vacuum, which was Something. Something contained infinite forms of energy, kinetic, dynamic, thermal, which are intangible. As well as the forces which are immaterial⁶, which appear in matter and at the same time as it.

GAS GRAINS

You know that all elements pass through the three states of matter depending on the heat imparted to them, solid, liquid and gas.

Water passes through the three states. When it is gaseous at 100 degrees Celsius, it becomes water vapor. Water vapor consists of granules of water molecules, and each grain consists of millions of molecules of water. This is indisputable.

And the elements, when in gaseous form, are made up of grains of molecules or atoms, possibly millions of them.

In the paper, we found that the hydrogen atom has a mass of the order of 10^{-32} kgr.⁷ And therefore mass of its grain, consisting of millions or thousands of hydrogen molecules, is in the order of 10^{-27} kgr.

In the mass spectrographs where the masses of the elements were found, those elements at normal temperature that were not gases, solids sublimated them or liquids evaporated them to become gases and make measurements. The gases consisted

⁶ FORCE AND MATTER, Wilchem Buchner

⁷ THE FINAL FORM OF THE ATOMIC THEORY, International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, Oct2023-Mar2023

of atom grains and found the masses of charged-ionized grains of the elements, not the atoms. It is possible that in the future the periodic table of elements will change, if we do not accept a fixed number of molecules or atoms that make up the grains. And because they found isotopes, the number of grains is not fixed. But in mass spectrographs, they found the masses of grains, not atoms. This means that in particle accelerators, grains of ionized elements accelerate and in collisions they break.

THE OPERATOR EQUATIONS OF CREATION OF THE ATOM AND HYDROGEN MOLECULE

From the paper THE FINAL FORM OF THE ATPMIC THEORY that we mentioned, published⁸ that the hydrogen equation is,

$$F = \frac{1}{2} \frac{k'e^2}{r^3} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\mu_0 I^2 (2\pi r)}{2\pi r} = kB_p e^2 \frac{v^2}{r} = kB_p e^2 \frac{d^2}{r^3}$$

Where, e=elementary charge, r=diameter of the orbiting equal bubbles-particles charged= $1,45 \times 10^{-8}$ met, about the other bubble particle of the atom at velocity c and simultaneously radius between the two charges, and $I=ef$ the current of the rotating bubble particle at a distance $l=2\pi r$ and B_p the magnetic field of the moving particle, acting on the other. Hydrogen gas, underwent an electrical voltage of 1000 Volts at 0.08 mbar.

In the privileged system of one bubble-particle, the other orbits circularly around the first, with radius r = diameter of the two grain bubbles in their center of mass system. And hence the centripetal $a=0.4v^2/r$. The integral of this equation with respect to Δr , for $\Delta r=r$ and at the same time be the other operator equation,

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \frac{k'e^2}{r^2} + \frac{\mu_0 I^2 r}{2} = kB_p e^2 \frac{c^2}{1} = kB_p e^2 \frac{d^2}{r^2}$$

If you consider the hydrogen molecule, they are two opposite electric rings with the same direction of particles, magnetically attracted by magnetic fields and the rings formed by charges, which also create electric fields. Then the molecule rotates at c speed of the bubble particles, not only within the atom, but as in the atom and about the axis between the rings, such as,

But in gas grains the hydrogen molecule does not have such behavior, but these are rings opposite, stationary. Orbiting identically and with identical charges opposite each other in the two rings and repulsive electrical force, but with attractive magnetic fields.

The equation is, $F = \frac{k'e^2}{r^3} = \frac{2\mu_0 I^2}{2}$ and r about 10^{-8} met, for low pressure.

Do not forget that we found these rays for a gas atom at high voltage and low pressure, less than 40 mmHg, i.e. for the pressure at Nt/met^2 less than $0.004 \times (1/760) = 5.26 \times 10^{-6}$ Atm $\times (5.007 \times 10^4) = 0.263$ Nt/met^2 .

⁸ Here a little corrected

OUR PLANETARY SYSTEM

ALL THE GYROSCOPES of the earth stand still 24 hours a day. This is proof that the earth does not revolve, neither around itself nor around the sun. But the whole universe revolves around the axis of the cosmos, which passes through the north and south poles of the earth.

We believe, as theories suggest, that the moon was cut off from the earth when it collided with a celestial body. Thus, the movement of the moon around the earth falls under the law of attraction that we indicated.

The moon orbits the earth in a period of $T = \{1 + (1/29.3)\} 86400 \text{ sec} = 89350 \text{ sec}$. The angular frequency is $\omega = 2\pi/T = 7 \times 10^{-5}$. And, $a = 0.4\omega^2 R = 0.75 \text{ Nt}$. The ratio factor is, $G_{\text{moon}} = 14.543 \text{ Nt.m}^{-2}.\text{met}^3$. The sun has a period around the earth $T = 86400 \text{ sec}$, distance $r = 1.496 \times 10^{11} \text{ met}$ and the acceleration is $0.4\omega^2 r = a = 316.4 \text{ met/sec}^2$. And it has a constant ratio $G = 1.45 \times 10^{14} \text{ Nt.m}^{-2}.\text{met}^3$

The two planets, Mercury and Venus, are satellites of the sun. The other planets orbit the earth circularly in about 86400 sec and simultaneously oscillate around the radius from the earth r_0 over a long period T_p , and the distance from the earth is $r_p = r_0 \cos(\omega t + \phi)$. Such an oscillation on a small scale. Both the moon and the sun do.

In the same period, planets that have a plane of rotation A make an oscillation perpendicular to the plane of orbit, $y = y_0 \cos(\omega t + \theta)$. So are the sun and moon.

In the same period, the planets make an oscillation $x = x_0 \cos(\omega t + u)$, around the planet's circular orbit point, in the plane of the orbit and perpendicular to the passenger radius of the orbit.

With an angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi/T$ and $T = 24 \text{ hours} = 86400 \text{ sec}$, then $\omega = 7.027 \times 10^{-5} \text{ rad/sec}$. And because the speed of light $c = \omega r$, it follows that within a radius of $4,125 \times 10^{12} \text{ met}$, the speed of rotation is at the speed of light. Beyond that is the third heaven and the second begins after the moon. There is no limitation of the theory of relativity, and celestial bodies have a speed faster than light.

The ether has mass. It behaves like⁹ a mass of gravity. That is why it affects celestial bodies, suns or planets in space, so that they move almost circularly around the axis of the cosmos. And it also has energy, the oscillating volume energy of points. These correspond to the dark mass and energy of space, already assumed by science.

THERMAL ENERGY

We know that the heat energy of a body of mass m is, $E = mc\Delta T$, c = the specific heat and T the temperature of the body. After the masses for the atoms we found in THE FINAL FORM OF THE ATOMIC THEORY, we consider a constant N , like Avogadro's and much larger, and N = the number of molecules or atoms of elements in a liter of gas, or in one mole or mole atom of mass m . Then $E/N = (m/N)c\Delta T = m_{Av}^2$, is the energy of the molecule (water, hydrogen, oxygen, etc.) or atom (monoatomic elements). This energy we divide by that of the constant h of physics and we will find the frequency of thermal oscillation of the molecule or atom, located between microwave and infrared frequencies.

EQUATION OF STATE AND STAR FORMATION CONDITIONS

According to physics, which I partially confirmed experimentally, the pressure of a gas at constant volume is $p = p_0(1 + a\theta)$, p_0 is the pressure of the gas at zero degrees Celsius, a is the fraction $1/273.16$ and θ is the temperature in degrees Celsius. And the volume of a gas at constant pressure is, $V = V_0(1 + a\theta)$ and V_0 is the volume of gas at zero degrees Celsius. Because both pressure and pressure can vary simultaneously volume, then the equation of state of gases is obtained, $pV = p_0 V_0(1 + a\theta)^2$.

If in a space of stellar space, a quantity of gas (hydrogen) is concentrated, then it becomes spherical and there is gravity $F = kMm/r^3$, where M is the total mass of gas that affects the mass m of the hydrogen molecule. In a critical amount of gas, the force F becomes greater than the difference $F_a - F_p$, where F_a is the cohesion strength of the molecules and F_p the repulsion force of molecules, which are usually magnetic moments of atoms. And the gas collapses, becomes dense and proceeds to create liquid matter that presses the inner gas and which in the core of the star becomes plasma. If the sun cools, it solidifies the crust with an inner mantle of liquid and much of the dense gases further inside and plasma at the center, such as the earth and planets.

⁹ Ernest Haeckel, Monism

A SUPERPHYSICS

The energy of the atom is a constant, constant velocity or acceleration, there is also initial conditions that are constant. If we multiply the constant by the unit, it does not change!

We know that some infinite series have the sum of the unit. Namely, $n=1,2,3,\dots,\infty$.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n} = 1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{16} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^n}$$

So the energy E, the velocity v, etc. is, $E=E\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n}$. Then we break down the constant into an infinite sum of terms that tend, have a limit of zero, and the constant springs from zero!

Plato said that nature is subject to genesis and decay, and we argue, because in decay the energy of matter decreases, that in the main sequence that has the sum of the unit, there are subsequences that some disappear and the energy of atoms is no longer constant, but some of them disappear and the energy decreases. In the superuniverses we will propose creation, there will be no decay and the sky will be bright. These are universes disks on the faces of pentagons in icosahedron.

THE CUBE OUR WORLD

The cube has an edge a, and the cube with the sphere inscribed in the crust of the central bubble ¹⁰corresponds to our world with $a/2=R$.

We consider an x, y, z, coordinate system of the central bubble.

We hold $r\cos\theta$ constant and rotate around the z-axis. Then the angle θ is of the original vector, but now it is $x^2+z^2=r'^2$ and r is the projection of r' , in the plane x, y. And $x=r'\cos\varphi$ and φ is the angle of r, r'

Vector r' , rotates around the z axis with radius $r'\cos\theta=r$, and r equal to the central bubble and forms a circle corresponding to a disk of one of the 6 universes of our cubic world.

One disk is of our universe, corresponding to the one seat of the cube of our world and has 6 disk universes with small disk thickness, each face of cube and three-dimensional time.

In our world we can have 3D rectilinear motion, which in the three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system, is,

$$x=x_0+v_1\Delta t \quad y=y_0+v_2\Delta t \quad z=z_0+v_3\Delta t$$

and,

$$\Delta t=(x-x_0)/v_1=(y-y_0)/v_2=(z-z_0)/v_3$$

the three same times corresponding to the three dimensions of space. One-dimensional time is a numerical quantity. And to the axes x,y,z, correspond the imaginary ix, iy, iz. And don't forget, that time, one-dimensional time is motion, uniformly repeated motion unit of time.

In the one-dimensional real world, the motion in the real world is on the radius R ($R=R_0+vt$) and the imaginary world on iR and respectively the times $\Delta t=(R-R_0)/v$, $\Delta t_i=(R_i-R_{0i})/v$ (4 dimensions in reality). Imaginary time is equivalent to real time and flows into dimensionless zero, within the imagination of the gods, It is the time of the gods. And she is determined for our dimensions of our universe, by the goddess.

¹⁰ A VEW OF THE WHOLE THAT ECHOES THE TOTAL THEORY, International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, April 22-September22

Each universe has dimensions of a circle, a circular disk and a very small disk thickness. The thickness of the circular disk corresponds to an ellipse, only it is almost a linear ellipse (when the eccentricity e of the ellipse approaches the unit, then the ellipse approaches the line). It's holography.

As we know, holography is formed when the rays emitted or reflected by a body, fall on the film and at the same time at an angle, ultraviolet rays fall on the same film.

This means that the ether at the seat of the cube where the rays fall is denser and acts like a film. This is how the circular disk of the universe is formed, which has a thickness of ellipse, almost linear. There is a long, spherical self-luminous universe, whose rays fall on the film. And another system of suns, emitting at an angle, ultraviolet radiation that falls on films. All six universes are thus formed and all universes, of all dimensions.

In the near-flat universe and all related universes of the same dimensions, space heterogeneity prevails and is not isotropic. And it is in cube seats the disks of our universes.

There are also six other universes of the same dimensions and conditions as those of the cube, and their disks are located in the regular hexahedron faces.

Regular hexahedron, the disks of the universes are located in the faces

The central bubble (blue), and within it, with the diameter-one-dimensional universe, the vertical circle two-dimensional universe and the regular tetrahedral three-dimensional universe, and besides four ellipsoidal sections of the four disk universes with the sphere pressed to have vertical ellipse-holographs of the six disk universes located in the cube inscribed with the bubble.

SUPERVERSES WITH THREE DIMENSIONS AND TWO DIMENSIONS OF THE SAME TIME

There are twelve superuniverses whose disks are located in the seats of a regular dodecahedron, which has the central bubble inscribed. The 12 universes intersect the 6 of the cube and the 6 of the hexahedron. They have common areas.

In these super-universes, the Olbers paradox occurs¹¹.

¹¹¹¹ ASTROPHYSICS H. Shou II, p. 139

In the seats of the regular dodecahedron are the disks of the 12 super-universes

Olbers' paradox is that the sky must be bright all day long because there are luminescent stars all over celestial space. And it happens there (in super-universes), because in these universes the ether is much thinner than ours. This is how the sky shines, all day long.

In our universes, stars radiate and light creates a disturbance of the ether, which disrupts an atom in the grains of interstellar gas, and they transmit the disturbance to the next ether, and again the disturbance falls into the next grain and disturbs its atom, and from now on. The resistance of the ether dampens the energy of the disturbance sequentially, and until it reaches us from distant stars, it does not become visible.

In the twelve super-universes the ether is much thinner and the sky is bright all day on the planets. That's where the Champs-Élysées go, where the morally excellent go.

The same time is determined by the goddess and god in their imagination and are the two dimensions of time, analyzed in each Cartesian coordinate system, where each of them works. That is, we have five dimensions in these super-universes, if we understand the times in the imagination of the two gods, as dimensions. And because this time, with the equations given, corresponds to the three dimensions of the universes, it is as if they are six dimensions, plus the three of the universes!

PARTIAL EQUATIONS-OPERATORS FOR CREATING UNIVERSES, COMPLETING CREATION

$$x=x_0+v_x t, y=y_0+v_y t, z=z_0+v_z t$$

$$v_x=a_x t, v_y=a_y t, v_z=a_z t$$

$$x=x_0+a_x t^2, y=y_0+a_y t^2, z=z_0+a_z t^2$$

$$\int_0^x F \Delta x = \int_0^x m a \Delta x = \int_0^x m \left(\frac{x}{t^2}\right) \Delta x = m v^2$$

$$F_c = 0.4 m \frac{v^2}{r}$$

$$I = m v = c, \text{ with no force effect on } m$$

On circular motions, $S = m(r \times v) = c$, without force effect on m

$$E = mgh = kmv^2$$

$$E = mv^2 \text{ for initial speed zero, exercise } F \text{ in } m.$$

$$E = Cx^2 = mv^2, \text{ spring-loaded, small oscillations, } \int_0^x Cx \Delta x$$

$$E = E \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n} \right)$$

$$F = kMm/r^3 = m.04v^2/r,$$

$r = r_0 \cos(\omega t)$ and perpendicular to the orbit, $r' = r_0' \cos(\omega t)$ and on the orbit, $r'' = r_0'' \cos(\omega t)$

$E =$ (the mathematics we entered was used).

$$E = \int_0^r \frac{kMm}{r^3} \Delta r = \frac{kMm}{r^2} = 0.4mv^2$$

$$p = p_0(1+a\theta), V = V_0(1+a\theta)$$

$$pV=p_0V_0(1+a\theta)^2$$

$$E=(m/N)c\Delta T= m_A v^2$$

$$I=e/t=q/t$$

$$E=k(m/e)v^2$$

$$V=k(m/n^2e^3)I^2$$

$$P=k(m/n^2e^3)I^3$$

$$F = \frac{\mu_0 I_1 I_2 l}{2\pi r}$$

$$F = \frac{e^2}{r^3}$$

$$F=I(lxB)$$

$$F=e(vxB)$$

$$m=kBe^2 \quad F = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{r^3} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 \frac{I^2(2\pi r)}{2\pi r} = \frac{mv^2}{r}$$

$$E = \int_0^r \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{r^3} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 \frac{I^2(2\pi r)}{r} \right\} \Delta r = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{r^2} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 \frac{I^2(2\pi r)}{1} = m_A v^2$$

$$V = \int_0^r \frac{e}{2r^3} \Delta r = \frac{e}{2r^2}$$

$$c=E/B$$

Field of straight electrical conductor $B = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2\pi r}$

circular electric loop field, in its center, $B = \frac{\mu_0 I}{r}$

EPILOGUE

With the calculus wrong, which we overturned, the wrong equations of the kinematic material body were derived. For the same reason it turned out to be a centripetal force, different from the real one we give and does not support the heliocentric system and Bohr's atom. Mistakes were made by Joule in the thermomechanical and thermoelectric equivalents and in the calculation of the power unit. The principle of conservation of energy, which is also overturned experimentally, does not apply. The geocentric system of the world is being restored. A new atomic theory is created, which stems from the author's worldview. A new form of electricity is created, challenging the strict acceptance of Ohm's law.

The correct centripetal force is demonstrated and the surface and volume formula of the ball is corrected.

It provides the structure of the universes predicted by my worldview and describes God's creation as incomplete. Operators-equations for the creation of superverses are proposed, which will act as molds of creation, as was done in the creation of matter by God.

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